

Interactive Ear Training – Web Audio API

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Figure 1: Interface of one of the exercises of the interactive ear training

ABSTRACT

Online video courses often lack interactions from the user. Yet, interactivity is a good way to engage people more in what they are learning. In the context of online courses that focus on audio, there are many tools that can be used to provide interactivity through the browser, one of them being the Web Audio API. This demo aims to show that the Web Audio API can be used for educational purposes, and more specifically making online courses more interactive and engaging for the user.

This project was carried out as part of an internship to see what level of interactivity was achievable in a given time. It is written using the Vue front-end framework, and takes advantage of the JavaScript Canvas API, to facilitate the visual gamification of the exercises.

1. The Interactive Ear Training

The interactive ear training is a web application and can be accessed from an internet browser. There are different exercises that are grouped by lesson. There are two different lessons: soloed and cut frequency bands, and boosted and cut frequencies.

For each exercise, a series of questions is presented to the user. For each question, the user listens to a random sound sample. By toggling a switch, the sample becomes filtered by an equaliser. The user must guess which filter was applied to the sound, only by using their hearing. After an answer is submitted, the correct answer is displayed and the score is incremented accordingly.

Figure 2: Interface of the first lesson

For the first lesson, the exercises concern frequency bands. For this category, there are four possible answers for every question. This makes it very accessible for people that have never done any ear training before.

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Figure 3: Interface of the second lesson

For the second lesson, the exercises display a whole equaliser, with the possible answers ranging from 20Hz to 20000Hz. This makes these exercises more challenging with a more complex scoring system.

2. The Equaliser

The main interaction in the second lesson of the ear training course is achieved with an equaliser graphically built with the Javascript Canvas API.

The audio processing on this equaliser is done using the Web Audio API Audio. The AudioContext allows the program to create and control AudioNodes. In our demo, the equalising is done using:

- A MediaElementSourceNode, for using samples as the input sound
- One or multiple BiquadFilterNodes, for filtering the sound depending on the filter's frequency and type
- An AnalyserNode, that has no effect on the sound but allows getting all the data necessary for visualisation

A bypass feature can be toggled by the user, which changes the audio routing graph to avoid going through the BiquadFilterNodes.

3. Settings for the Demo

The interactive ear training can be used in most modern browsers, but for the best experience, we recommend using Google Chrome or Mozilla Firefox on Windows 10.